

Some Conformable Fractional Newton-type Inequalities via Bounded and Lipschitzian Functions

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Abstract

The core purpose of this study is to investigate some Newton-type inequalities in the framework of conformable fractional operators. These type of inequalities are established for bounded functions and further results are obtained for Lipschitzian functions. In this way, the classical Newton-type inequalities are extended through the perspective of fractional analysis. Moreover, through specific selections of the obtained inequalities, further results are derived, which emphasize the versatility and practical applicability of the proposed approach. Overall, this study adds to the literature on fractional analysis and functional inequalities and also provides a basis for future work in this area.

Keywords: Newton-type inequalities, bounded functions, Lipschitzian functions.

1 Introduction and Basic Concepts

The Hermite-Hadamard and Simpson-type inequalities have received significant attention in recent years. In particular, Simpson-type inequalities are derived from Simpson's classical rule in numerical integration. Simpson's second rule corresponds to the three-point Newton-Cotes quadrature formula. As a result, evaluations involving a quadratic kernel with three nodes are often referred to as Newton-type results, which are commonly known in the literature as Newton-type inequalities. These inequalities have been extensively studied by numerous researchers. For instance, Gao and Shi [1] proved some Newton-type inequalities for functions whose second derivatives are convex. In paper [2], some error estimates of Newton-type quadrature formula by bounded variation and Lipschitzian functions were considered. Moreover, Noor et al. investigated Newton-type inequalities related to harmonic convex functions in [3], and to p -harmonic convex functions in [4]. In [5], some Newton-type inequalities established by convex functions within the framework of quantum calculus. For more information and unresolved questions on Newton-type inequalities, see [6, 7] and the references cited therein.

Fractional calculus has attracted significant interest recently due to its wide applications across various scientific fields. In response to its importance, many fractional integral operators have been introduced and studied. Using Hermite–Hadamard-type and Simpson-type inequalities, bounds for these newly developed formulas can be established. Notably, Hermite–Hadamard-type and trapezoidal-type inequalities were first explored with Riemann-Liouville fractional integrals in [8].

Definition 1.1 (See [9, 10]). Let $f \in L_1[a, b]$, $a, b \in \mathbb{R}$ with $a < b$. The Riemann-Liouville fractional integrals $J_{a+}^\beta f$ and $J_{b-}^\beta f$ of order $\beta > 0$ are defined by

$$J_{a+}^\beta f(x) = \frac{1}{\Gamma(\beta)} \int_a^x (x-t)^{\beta-1} f(t) dt, \quad x > a \quad (1)$$

and

$$J_{b-}^\beta f(x) = \frac{1}{\Gamma(\beta)} \int_x^b (t-x)^{\beta-1} f(t) dt, \quad x < b, \quad (2)$$

respectively. Here, Γ denotes the Gamma function defined by

$$\Gamma(\beta) = \int_0^\infty e^{-u} u^{\beta-1} du.$$

Let us note that $J_{a+}^0 f(x) = J_{b-}^0 f(x) = f(x)$.

The paper [11] presents several Newton-type inequalities for differentiable convex functions derived using Riemann-Liouville fractional integrals. Additionally, the authors obtained Riemann-Liouville fractional Newton-type inequalities for functions of bounded variation. Moreover, in [12], the authors derived several Newton-type inequalities for functions whose absolute first derivatives, raised to a given power, satisfy the condition of arithmetic-harmonic convexity. Furthermore, the authors of [13] present a method to investigate Newton-type inequalities for various classes of functions using Riemann-Liouville fractional integrals. These inequalities have been further explored by numerous researchers (see, for instance, [14, 15] and the references therein).

Various types of fractional integrals, including Riemann-Liouville and conformable fractional integrals, have been studied in the context of integral inequalities. The expanding applications of these concepts have recently attracted considerable interest from researchers in mathematics, physics, and engineering [16, 17]. Moreover, fractional derivatives are also used to model a wide range of mathematical biology, as well as chemical processes and engineering problems [18, 19]. In [20], the authors introduced a new type of fractional derivative called the conformable derivative, based on the fundamental limit definition of the standard derivative. This operator possesses several useful analytical properties. The conformable derivative satisfies several key properties that are not fulfilled by the Riemann-Liouville and Caputo definitions. In paper [21] the author proved that the conformable approach in [20] cannot yield good results when compared to the Caputo definition for specific functions. This limitation of the conformable derivative has been addressed through several extensions of the conformable approach, as proposed in [22, 23].

In [24], the authors introduced fractional conformable integral operators and studied several of their fundamental properties. They also examined the relationships between these operators and other existing fractional integral definitions. The fractional conformable integral operators are defined as follows:

Definition 1.2. [24] The fractional conformable integral operator ${}^\beta \mathcal{J}_{a+}^\alpha f(x)$ and ${}^\beta \mathcal{J}_{b-}^\alpha f(x)$ of order $\beta \in \mathbb{C}$, $\operatorname{Re}(\beta) > 0$ and $\alpha \in (0, 1]$ are presented by

$${}^\beta \mathcal{J}_{a+}^\alpha f(x) = \frac{1}{\Gamma(\beta)} \int_a^x \left(\frac{(x-a)^\alpha - (t-a)^\alpha}{\alpha} \right)^{\beta-1} \frac{f(t)}{(t-a)^{1-\alpha}} dt, \quad t > a \quad (3)$$

and

$${}^\beta \mathcal{J}_{b-}^\alpha f(x) = \frac{1}{\Gamma(\beta)} \int_x^b \left(\frac{(b-x)^\alpha - (b-t)^\alpha}{\alpha} \right)^{\beta-1} \frac{f(t)}{(b-t)^{1-\alpha}} dt, \quad t < b, \quad (4)$$

respectively for $f \in L_1[a, b]$.

If we consider $\alpha = 1$ in equalities (3) and (4), then the fractional integral in (3) and (4) reduces to the Riemann-Liouville fractional integral in (1) and (2), respectively. There have been a great number of research papers written on these subjects, [25, 26] and the references therein.

2 A fundamental equality

Lemma 2.1. Assume that $f : [a, b] \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ is an absolutely continuous function (a, b) so that $f' \in L_1[a, b]$. Then, the following equality holds:

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{1}{8} \left[f(a) + 3f\left(\frac{2a+b}{3}\right) + 3f\left(\frac{a+2b}{3}\right) + f(b) \right] - \frac{\alpha^\beta \Gamma(\alpha+1)}{2(b-a)^{\alpha\beta}} \left[{}^\beta \mathcal{J}_{b-}^\alpha f(a) + {}^\beta \mathcal{J}_{a+}^\alpha f(b) \right] \quad (5) \\ & = \frac{\alpha^\beta (b-a)}{2} [I_1 + I_2 + I_3]. \end{aligned}$$

Here,

$$\begin{cases} I_1 = \int_0^{\frac{1}{3}} \left[\left(\frac{1-(1-t)^\alpha}{\alpha} \right)^\beta - \frac{1}{8\alpha^\beta} \right] [f'(tb + (1-t)a) - f'(ta + (1-t)b)] dt, \\ I_2 = \int_{\frac{1}{3}}^{\frac{2}{3}} \left[\left(\frac{1-(1-t)^\alpha}{\alpha} \right)^\beta - \frac{1}{2\alpha^\beta} \right] [f'(tb + (1-t)a) - f'(ta + (1-t)b)] dt, \\ I_3 = \int_{\frac{2}{3}}^1 \left[\left(\frac{1-(1-t)^\alpha}{\alpha} \right)^\beta - \frac{7}{8\alpha^\beta} \right] [f'(tb + (1-t)a) - f'(ta + (1-t)b)] dt. \end{cases}$$

3 Newton-type inequalities for bounded functions

In this section, we deal with some Newton-type inequalities for bounded functions via conformable fractional integrals.

Theorem 3.1. Note that the conditions of Lemma 2.1 hold. If there exist $m, M \in \mathbb{R}$ such that

$m \leq f'(t) \leq M$ for $t \in [a, b]$, then it follows

$$\begin{aligned} & \left| \frac{1}{8} \left[f(a) + 3f\left(\frac{2a+b}{3}\right) + 3f\left(\frac{a+2b}{3}\right) + f(b) \right] \right. \\ & \left. - \frac{\alpha^\beta \Gamma(\alpha+1)}{2(b-a)^{\alpha\beta}} \left[{}^\beta \mathcal{J}_{b-}^\alpha f(a) + {}^\beta \mathcal{J}_{a+}^\alpha f(b) \right] \right| \\ & \leq \frac{\alpha^\beta (b-a)}{2} \{ \Omega_1(\alpha, \beta) + \Omega_2(\alpha, \beta) + \Omega_3(\alpha, \beta) \} (M-m). \end{aligned} \tag{6}$$

Here,

$$\begin{cases} \Omega_1(\alpha, \beta) = \int_0^{\frac{1}{3}} \left| \left(\frac{1-(1-t)^\alpha}{\alpha} \right)^\beta - \frac{1}{8\alpha^\beta} \right| dt, \\ \Omega_2(\alpha, \beta) = \int_{\frac{1}{3}}^{\frac{2}{3}} \left| \left(\frac{1-(1-t)^\alpha}{\alpha} \right)^\beta - \frac{1}{2\alpha^\beta} \right| dt, \\ \Omega_3(\alpha, \beta) = \int_{\frac{2}{3}}^1 \left| \left(\frac{1-(1-t)^\alpha}{\alpha} \right)^\beta - \frac{7}{8\alpha^\beta} \right| dt. \end{cases}$$

Proof. By using the Lemma 2.1, we have

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{1}{8} \left[f(a) + 3f\left(\frac{2a+b}{3}\right) + 3f\left(\frac{a+2b}{3}\right) + f(b) \right] \\ & - \frac{\alpha^\beta \Gamma(\alpha+1)}{2(b-a)^{\alpha\beta}} \left[{}^\beta \mathcal{J}_{b-}^\alpha f(a) + {}^\beta \mathcal{J}_{a+}^\alpha f(b) \right] \\ & = \frac{\alpha^\beta (b-a)}{2} \left\{ \int_0^{\frac{1}{3}} \left[\left(\frac{1-(1-t)^\alpha}{\alpha} \right)^\beta - \frac{1}{8\alpha^\beta} \right] \left[f'(tb + (1-t)a) - \frac{m+M}{2} \right] dt \right. \\ & \quad + \int_0^{\frac{1}{3}} \left[\left(\frac{1-(1-t)^\alpha}{\alpha} \right)^\beta - \frac{1}{8\alpha^\beta} \right] \left[\frac{m+M}{2} - f'(ta + (1-t)b) \right] dt \\ & \quad + \int_{\frac{1}{3}}^{\frac{2}{3}} \left[\left(\frac{1-(1-t)^\alpha}{\alpha} \right)^\beta - \frac{1}{2\alpha^\beta} \right] \left[f'(tb + (1-t)a) - \frac{m+M}{2} \right] dt \\ & \quad + \int_{\frac{1}{3}}^{\frac{2}{3}} \left[\left(\frac{1-(1-t)^\alpha}{\alpha} \right)^\beta - \frac{1}{2\alpha^\beta} \right] \left[\frac{m+M}{2} - f'(ta + (1-t)b) \right] dt \\ & \quad + \int_{\frac{2}{3}}^1 \left[\left(\frac{1-(1-t)^\alpha}{\alpha} \right)^\beta - \frac{7}{8\alpha^\beta} \right] \left[f'(tb + (1-t)a) - \frac{m+M}{2} \right] dt \\ & \quad \left. + \int_{\frac{2}{3}}^1 \left[\left(\frac{1-(1-t)^\alpha}{\alpha} \right)^\beta - \frac{7}{8\alpha^\beta} \right] \left[\frac{m+M}{2} - f'(ta + (1-t)b) \right] dt \right\}. \end{aligned} \tag{7}$$

Through the absolute value of (7), we get

$$\begin{aligned} & \left| \frac{1}{8} \left[f(a) + 3f\left(\frac{2a+b}{3}\right) + 3f\left(\frac{a+2b}{3}\right) + f(b) \right] \right. \\ & \left. - \frac{\alpha^\beta \Gamma(\alpha+1)}{2(b-a)^{\alpha\beta}} \left[{}^\beta \mathcal{J}_{b-}^\alpha f(a) + {}^\beta \mathcal{J}_{a+}^\alpha f(b) \right] \right| \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
&\leq \frac{\alpha^\beta (b-a)}{2} \left\{ \int_0^{\frac{1}{3}} \left| \left(\frac{1-(1-t)^\alpha}{\alpha} \right)^\beta - \frac{1}{8\alpha^\beta} \right| \left| f'(tb+(1-t)a) - \frac{m+M}{2} \right| dt \right. \\
&\quad + \int_0^{\frac{1}{3}} \left| \left(\frac{1-(1-t)^\alpha}{\alpha} \right)^\beta - \frac{1}{8\alpha^\beta} \right| \left| \frac{m+M}{2} - f'(ta+(1-t)b) \right| dt \\
&\quad + \int_{\frac{1}{3}}^{\frac{2}{3}} \left| \left(\frac{1-(1-t)^\alpha}{\alpha} \right)^\beta - \frac{1}{2\alpha^\beta} \right| \left| f'(tb+(1-t)a) - \frac{m+M}{2} \right| dt \\
&\quad + \int_{\frac{1}{3}}^{\frac{2}{3}} \left| \left(\frac{1-(1-t)^\alpha}{\alpha} \right)^\beta - \frac{1}{2\alpha^\beta} \right| \left| \frac{m+M}{2} - f'(ta+(1-t)b) \right| dt \\
&\quad + \int_{\frac{2}{3}}^1 \left| \left(\frac{1-(1-t)^\alpha}{\alpha} \right)^\beta - \frac{7}{8\alpha^\beta} \right| \left| f'(tb+(1-t)a) - \frac{m+M}{2} \right| dt \\
&\quad \left. + \int_{\frac{2}{3}}^1 \left| \left(\frac{1-(1-t)^\alpha}{\alpha} \right)^\beta - \frac{7}{8\alpha^\beta} \right| \left| \frac{m+M}{2} - f'(ta+(1-t)b) \right| dt \right\}.
\end{aligned}$$

It is known that $m \leq f'(t) \leq M$ for $t \in [a, b]$. Then, we have

$$\left| f'(tb+(1-t)a) - \frac{m+M}{2} \right| \leq \frac{M-m}{2}, \tag{8}$$

$$\left| \frac{m+M}{2} - f'(ta+(1-t)b) \right| \leq \frac{M-m}{2}. \tag{9}$$

With the help of the (8) and (9), we obtain

$$\begin{aligned}
&\left| \frac{1}{8} \left[f(a) + 3f\left(\frac{2a+b}{3}\right) + 3f\left(\frac{a+2b}{3}\right) + f(b) \right] \right. \\
&\quad \left. - \frac{\alpha^\beta \Gamma(\alpha+1)}{2(b-a)^{\alpha\beta}} \left[{}^\beta \mathcal{J}_{b^-}^\alpha f(a) + {}^\beta \mathcal{J}_{a^+}^\alpha f(b) \right] \right| \\
&\leq \frac{\alpha^\beta (b-a)}{2} (M-m) \\
&\quad \times \left\{ \int_0^{\frac{1}{3}} \left| \left(\frac{1-(1-t)^\alpha}{\alpha} \right)^\beta - \frac{1}{8\alpha^\beta} \right| dt \right. \\
&\quad \left. + \int_{\frac{1}{3}}^{\frac{2}{3}} \left| \left(\frac{1-(1-t)^\alpha}{\alpha} \right)^\beta - \frac{1}{2\alpha^\beta} \right| dt + \int_{\frac{2}{3}}^1 \left| \left(\frac{1-(1-t)^\alpha}{\alpha} \right)^\beta - \frac{7}{8\alpha^\beta} \right| dt \right\} \\
&= \frac{\alpha^\beta (b-a)}{2} \{ \Omega_1(\alpha, \beta) + \Omega_2(\alpha, \beta) + \Omega_3(\alpha, \beta) \} (M-m).
\end{aligned}$$

□

Corollary 3.1. If we choose $\alpha = \beta = 1$ in Theorem 3.1, then we get

$$\begin{aligned} & \left| \frac{1}{8} \left[f(a) + 3f\left(\frac{2a+b}{3}\right) + 3f\left(\frac{a+2b}{3}\right) + f(b) \right] - \frac{1}{b-a} \int_a^b f(t) dt \right| \\ & \leq \frac{25(b-a)}{576} (M-m). \end{aligned}$$

Corollary 3.2. Let us consider $\alpha = 1$ Theorem 3.1. If there exist $M \in \mathbb{R}^+$ such that $|f'(t)| \leq M$ for all $t \in [a, b]$, then we have

$$\begin{aligned} & \left| \frac{1}{8} \left[f(a) + 3f\left(\frac{2a+b}{3}\right) + 3f\left(\frac{a+2b}{3}\right) + f(b) \right] \right. \\ & \quad \left. - \frac{\Gamma(\beta+1)}{2(b-a)^\beta} [J_{a+}^\beta f(b) + J_{b-}^\beta f(a)] \right| \\ & \leq \frac{b-a}{2} \{ \Omega_1(1, \beta) + \Omega_2(1, \beta) + \Omega_3(1, \beta) \} M. \end{aligned}$$

Corollary 3.3. Let us consider $\beta = 1$ in Corollary 3.2. Then, the following inequality holds:

$$\begin{aligned} & \left| \frac{1}{8} \left[f(a) + 3f\left(\frac{2a+b}{3}\right) + 3f\left(\frac{a+2b}{3}\right) + f(b) \right] - \frac{1}{b-a} \int_a^b f(t) dt \right| \\ & \leq \frac{25(b-a)}{288} M. \end{aligned}$$

4 Newton-type inequalities for Lipschitzian functions

In this section, we consider some Newton-type inequalities for Lipschitzian functions by using conformable fractional integrals.

Theorem 4.1. Suppose that the assumptions of Lemma 2.1 are valid. If f' is a L -Lipschitzian function on $[a, b]$, then the following inequality holds:

$$\begin{aligned} & \left| \frac{1}{8} \left[f(a) + 3f\left(\frac{2a+b}{3}\right) + 3f\left(\frac{a+2b}{3}\right) + f(b) \right] \right. \\ & \quad \left. - \frac{\alpha^\beta \Gamma(\alpha+1)}{2(b-a)^{\alpha\beta}} \left[{}^\beta \mathcal{J}_{b-}^\alpha f(a) + {}^\beta \mathcal{J}_{a+}^\alpha f(b) \right] \right| \leq \frac{\alpha^\beta (b-a)^2}{2} L \\ & \quad \times \{ 2\Omega_4(\alpha, \beta) - \Omega_1(\alpha, \beta) + 2\Omega_5(\alpha, \beta) - \Omega_2(\alpha, \beta) \\ & \quad + 2\Omega_6(\alpha, \beta) - \Omega_3(\alpha, \beta) \}. \end{aligned}$$

Here,

$$\begin{cases} \Omega_4(\alpha, \beta) = \int_0^{\frac{1}{3}} t \left| \left(\frac{1-(1-t)^\alpha}{\alpha} \right)^\beta - \frac{1}{8\alpha^\beta} \right| dt, \\ \Omega_5(\alpha, \beta) = \int_{\frac{1}{3}}^{\frac{2}{3}} t \left| \left(\frac{1-(1-t)^\alpha}{\alpha} \right)^\beta - \frac{1}{2\alpha^\beta} \right| dt, \\ \Omega_6(\alpha, \beta) = \int_{\frac{2}{3}}^1 t \left| \left(\frac{1-(1-t)^\alpha}{\alpha} \right)^\beta - \frac{7}{8\alpha^\beta} \right| dt. \end{cases}$$

Proof. With the aid of Lemma 2.1 and since f' is L -Lipschitzian function, we have

$$\left| \frac{1}{8} \left[f(a) + 3f\left(\frac{2a+b}{3}\right) + 3f\left(\frac{a+2b}{3}\right) + f(b) \right] \right|$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& -\frac{\alpha^\beta \Gamma(\alpha+1)}{2(b-a)^{\alpha\beta}} \left[{}^\beta \mathcal{J}_{b^-}^\alpha f(a) + {}^\beta \mathcal{J}_{a^+}^\alpha f(b) \right] \Big| = \left| \frac{\alpha^\beta (b-a)}{2} \right. \\
& \times \left\{ \int_0^{\frac{1}{3}} \left[\left(\frac{1-(1-t)^\alpha}{\alpha} \right)^\beta - \frac{1}{8\alpha^\beta} \right] [f'(tb+(1-t)a) - f'(ta+(1-t)b)] dt \right. \\
& + \int_{\frac{1}{3}}^{\frac{2}{3}} \left[\left(\frac{1-(1-t)^\alpha}{\alpha} \right)^\beta - \frac{1}{2\alpha^\beta} \right] [f'(tb+(1-t)a) - f'(ta+(1-t)b)] dt \\
& \left. + \int_{\frac{2}{3}}^1 \left[\left(\frac{1-(1-t)^\alpha}{\alpha} \right)^\beta - \frac{7}{8\alpha^\beta} \right] [f'(tb+(1-t)a) - f'(ta+(1-t)b)] dt \right\} \Big| \\
& \leq \frac{\alpha^\beta (b-a)}{2} \left\{ \int_0^{\frac{1}{3}} \left| \left(\frac{1-(1-t)^\alpha}{\alpha} \right)^\beta - \frac{1}{8\alpha^\beta} \right| |f'(tb+(1-t)a) - f'(ta+(1-t)b)| dt \right. \\
& + \int_{\frac{1}{3}}^{\frac{2}{3}} \left| \left(\frac{1-(1-t)^\alpha}{\alpha} \right)^\beta - \frac{1}{2\alpha^\beta} \right| |f'(tb+(1-t)a) - f'(ta+(1-t)b)| dt \\
& \left. + \int_{\frac{2}{3}}^1 \left| \left(\frac{1-(1-t)^\alpha}{\alpha} \right)^\beta - \frac{7}{8\alpha^\beta} \right| |f'(tb+(1-t)a) - f'(ta+(1-t)b)| dt \right\} \\
& \leq \frac{\alpha^\beta (b-a)}{2} \left\{ \int_0^{\frac{1}{3}} \left| \left(\frac{1-(1-t)^\alpha}{\alpha} \right)^\beta - \frac{1}{8\alpha^\beta} \right| L(2t-1)(b-a) dt \right. \\
& + \int_{\frac{1}{3}}^{\frac{2}{3}} \left| \left(\frac{1-(1-t)^\alpha}{\alpha} \right)^\beta - \frac{1}{2\alpha^\beta} \right| L(2t-1)(b-a) dt \\
& \left. + \int_{\frac{2}{3}}^1 \left| \left(\frac{1-(1-t)^\alpha}{\alpha} \right)^\beta - \frac{7}{8\alpha^\beta} \right| L(2t-1)(b-a) dt \right\} = \frac{\alpha^\beta (b-a)^2}{2} L \\
& \times \{ 2\Omega_4(\alpha, \beta) - \Omega_1(\alpha, \beta) + 2\Omega_5(\alpha, \beta) - \Omega_2(\alpha, \beta) \\
& + 2\Omega_6(\alpha, \beta) - \Omega_3(\alpha, \beta) \}.
\end{aligned}$$

□

Corollary 4.1. Consider $\alpha = \beta = 1$ in Theorem 4.1. Then, the following Newton-type inequality holds:

$$\begin{aligned}
& \left| \frac{1}{8} \left[f(a) + 3f\left(\frac{2a+b}{3}\right) + 3f\left(\frac{a+2b}{3}\right) + f(b) \right] - \frac{1}{b-a} \int_a^b f(t) dt \right| \\
& \leq \frac{475(b-a)^2}{20736} L.
\end{aligned}$$

5 Concluding remarks

In this paper, we establish several Newton-type inequalities related to conformable fractional operators for bounded functions. Additionally, we derive Newton-type inequalities for Lipschitzian functions. Furthermore, we present some results based on special cases of the obtained inequalities.

In future work, the ideas and methods used in our results on Newton-type inequalities involving conformable fractional integrals may open new directions for researchers in this field. Moreover, these results can be generalized by considering different classes of convex functions or alternative types of fractional integral operators. Additionally, similar inequalities for convex functions using conformable fractional integrals could be explored through quantum calculus.

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